

Stock Price Informativeness and Profit Warnings: Empirical Analysis

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ABSTRACT: This study investigates the nature of association between profit warnings and stock price informativeness in the context of Jordan as an emerging country. The analysis is based on the response of stock price synchronicity to profit warnings percentages that have been published in Jordanian firms throughout the period spanning 2005–2016 in the Amman Stock Exchange. The standard of profit warnings indicators have related negatively to stock price synchronicity in Jordanian firms, meaning that firms with a high portion of profit warnings integrate with more firm-specific information into stock price. Robust regression was used rather than OLS as a parametric test to overcome the variances inflation factor (VIF) and heteroscedasticity issues recognized as having occurred during running the OLS regression; this enabled us to obtain stronger results that fall in line with our prediction that higher profit warning encourages firm investors to collect and process more firm-specific information than common market information.

KEYWORDS: Profit Warnings, Jordanian Firms, Stock Price Informativeness, Synchronicity, Whites Robust Regression

JEL Classification: M41, G14

1. Introduction

Profit warnings are recognized as referring to the announcements made by publicly listed entities prior to the presentation of their formal financial statements with the aim of warning shareholders that their earnings will be in difference to previously expected levels. Profit warnings can be either positive or negative. The current research investigates whether or not there is a reaction between market behavior and profit warnings. This issue has previously faced heated debates from UK and US pioneers.

Attracting investors is deemed to be an important issue for firms seeking to increase their capital in order to extend their investments and dominate the market. This, in turn, has led firms to pay more attention to their stock price. High stock price is more likely to lead to increased investor returns (Penman, 2009). Several prior studies present that the difference in stock price is more noticeable when timed around important news declarations (e.g., Yin, Mazouz, Benamraoui & Saadouni, 2018). In addition, Lui, Markov & Tamayo (2013) find that the organized risk of individual stocks responds disproportionately to the good and bad news included within the predictor reports. Likewise, Zolotoy (2011) debates that the equity value has a habit of increasing (decreasing) following the appearance of good (bad) news, particularly when debt provision directs downwards (upwards). For example, the announcement of optimistic (undesirable) news led to decreases (increases) in the portion of risk for equity investments.

Empirical evidence presented on stock price reaction to profit warnings is restricted to developed markets, such as those of the UK, the US and China. For example, Lui *et al.* (2013) find that stock prices exaggerate with profit warnings, particularly in line with announced negative news (e.g., China reports a significant –3% price drop, over the period of approximately a [–1 to 1] window, and a significant 7.81% increase in stock prices over the period amounting to a [+2 to +60] window in regards negative profit warnings. Accordingly, this study contributes to the prior literature in different ways: first, through studying new emerging markets where the

majority of prior studies have focused their attention to cover developed countries; this, in turn, led to covering the gaps that could arise in the future since our results are consistent with prior literature (e.g., Yin *et al.* 2018; Lui, *et al.* 2013); second, emerging markets have provided empirical results with a similar criteria of developed markets, which allows the researchers to compare the results in developing markets with developed markets. Finally, comparing the empirical results between developing markets and developed markets increases the opportunities of exploring several factors that could potentially affect the results in developing markets in relation to influencing profit warnings on stock prices, such as political and economic circumstances, legal systems, and cultural factors.

In conclusion, this study aims to establish the relationship between profit warnings and stock prices in Jordanian firms throughout the period 2005–2016, which includes 810 firm-years. However, a quantitative approach was adopted in order to explore the association between profit warnings and stock price. Our results show that profit warnings amongst Jordanian firms have a significant negative relationship with stock price synchronicity, meaning that the higher portion of profit warnings is more likely to lead to firm specific information in terms of stock price synchronicity. These results are consistent with prior literature, as can be seen in the works of Kim & Yi (2015) and Yu, Li, Tian & Zhang (2013) in regards firms' financial leverage, equity ratio and industrial type, which show a significant negative effect on stock price synchronicity. On the other hand, return on equity and market-to-book value has a significant positive relationship with stock price synchronicity.

2. Literature Review

In order to understand more specifically about how profit warning is defined, we firstly consider a few definitions from previous literatures. Elayan & Pukthuanthong (2009) define profit warning as a notice released by firms, and it exposes that earnings are lower than expected earnings. According to Skinner (1994), profit warning is recognized as an important tool issued by firm management in order to reduce litigation and reputation costs. Managing profit warning can occur at any time throughout the financial year, particularly before the publishing of an actual profit report, and the management of profit warning might be in several types of accounting terms, such as Earnings Per Share (EPS), sales, and Profit Before Interest and Tax (PBIT) (Elayan *et al.* 2009). Bulkley & Herrerias (2004) define profit warning as an unpredicted firm declaration, where regulatory approaching earnings period could lead to a decrease in the present prospectation. Furthermore, they state that profit warnings are clean information as opposed to the data the firm produces as a decision in order to direct material penalty.

The main justification for the profit warnings phenomena is that the marketplace is under a number of different circumstances, such as economics, political and cultural. Profit warnings are considered to be one of the issues related to earnings surprises, except for the reality of the unanticipated issue associated with similar drift. Furthermore, profit warnings are correlated to earning announcements, including disclosure, where the main difference between profit warnings (PWs) and earnings announcement (EA) is the determination (PW is unexpected and EA is determined) (Kiminda, 2014).

Prior literature categorized profit warning onto two types: first, quantitative warnings, which include obvious numbers and exact approximation profit amount; the second type is qualitative, which is revealed as non-numeric information that expects that profit warnings will occur in the firm in the nearest future (Skinner, 1994). A number of different environments could be better than others when it comes to disclosing financial information. For instance, on the evening of December 4, 2000, 3Com Corp issued a profit warning on the top of a long bull market. The next morning, its share price dropped by almost 30 per cent with an abnormal return of –32.5 per cent. Furthermore, in early-2001, PW issued profit warnings, which led to reduced stock price amounting to 21 per cent, with an abnormal return of –4.7 per cent (Cox *et al.* 2017).

DeStefano (2004) documented that the prior literature has determined that the understanding of bad news has changed over the business cycle, which means that there are differences in profit warnings and their effects on business transactions across each unit.

Jackson & Madura (2003) found that the time period preceding the earnings announcement does not give any indication of profit warnings. On the other hand, they found that share prices seem to change five days before a profit warning, which means that stock price is considered to be the first item in financial statements that is impacted by profit warnings announcements. Several factors were documented in the prior literature that could potentially influence profit warnings. Empirical analyses of Aubert & Louhichi (2015), for example, indicate that firm legal information environment and the index of investors in each country have different impacts on profit warnings announcements; this is rationalised by their study, which they applied to four countries (France, Germany, the Netherlands and the UK) based on a sample of 1,330 profit warnings issued during the period 2000–2010. The firm's legal information environment and investors' index supported the researcher in developing an analytical forecasting model to predict profit warnings.

Chen & Mohan (1994) debate that managers motivate the period of releasing bad news in order to mitigate the negative market response, particularly when managers issue profit warnings. In fact, managers have more information about expected profit in firms than investors; however, managers refuse to announce that there is a profit warnings in case of appearing short in profitability, particularly when it is 3–4 weeks prior to announcing formal earnings, where profit warnings are more likely to be different from one firm to another, and from one point in time to another (Cox, Dayanandan, Donker & Nofsinger 2017).

Announcing profit warnings can lead to negative effects for banking industry conditions, where Jackson & Madura (2004) found that banks experience negative assessment impacts in reaction to their profit warnings, and also document negative impacts on share price in banks before and after the issuance of profit warnings. This, in turn, led to investors relying on more obvious sources of information pertaining to individual banks rather than relying on one bank's warning as indicators for other banks.

In most cases, management prefer to issue profit warnings in times of difficult circumstance that could face firms. Kearns & Whitley (2002) found that profit warnings are headed by decreases in firm profit margins; this is greater amongst firms with negative profits compared with firms with positive profit. Several prior studies related to profit warnings propose that the large portion of negative earnings is produced from announcing bad news that is unexpected and could be avoided through the issuance of incentives from management (e.g., Spohr, 2014; Kothari, Shu & Wysocki, 2009). Accordingly, Xu (2008) states that the announcement of profit warnings is more likely related to reductions in stock prices.

Clare (2001) used the UK data to test whether investors tend to overreact more to negative warnings than to positive ones. In the same regard, in line with the overreaction hypothesis, Tucker (2004) shows that investors react more negatively to firms that warn when they anticipate negative earnings news than to those that do not provide warnings. Moreover, Jackson & Madura (2003) examine stock price behaviour in regards important profit warnings containing negative ones in the US market. The researchers detailed a significant price drop of –21.7% over an 11-day period ending 5 days following the announcement. However, the results show no evidence of reversal after this window of event, and accordingly conclude that the market reaction to negative warnings is not reasonable.

As noticed, the above reference to the UK and US research uses the basic event study and somehow ignores the interaction between shares released information and the variation of stock Betas that are strongly documented within the literature (Lui *et al.* 2009; Savickas 2003; Zolotoy 2011; Cam & Ramiah 2014).

The information content is fundamentally linked to the efficient market hypothesis. Within this hypothesis, particularly the semi-strong form (where share prices are expected to reflect all available accounting information, including the present value of future cash flows), accounting numbers have information content should security prices respond to released data (Wolk *et al.* 2001). Furthermore, Ball & Brown (1968, p. 161) state that ‘an observed revision of stock prices associated with the release of the income report would thus provide evidence that the information reflected in income numbers is useful’.

Thus, financial reporting is intended to provide information to help investors, creditors and other parties to assess the stewardship of the entity’s management and the amounts, timing and uncertainty of prospective cash flows to the related enterprise. The financial information released is considered to have information content if it is useful for economic decision-making and has some impacts on firms’ share prices. Hence, unlike previous research, the current research will use the accounting figures needed in order to investigate the association between performance measures with stock price and stock returns, as published in the financial lists, rather than the use of proxies. The fact should be raised here that it is quite difficult to understand the information content of the accounting figures without considering the characteristics of the reliability and relevancy of such accounting data. Financial information is said to be relevant if it influences the economic decisions of users, which can be achieved by helping them to evaluate past, present and future, which it does if it has predictive or confirmatory value. Relevance and faithful representation are the key characteristics of useful financial information. The faithful representation should be neutral, free from error, and complete (IASB, Conceptual Framework of Financial Reporting, 2011).

Formally, information content, valuation relevance and value relevance are the three main approaches to have emerged in the last three decades for examining the effect of accounting information on financial markets. Lo & Thomas (2000) show that information content has remained constant whilst valuation relevance and value relevance have both declined with respect to return volatility and the non-linearity of the valuation models used (earnings composition model and the earnings expectation model).

Historically, three primary approaches were used to investigate the implication of accounting disclosures for security prices: the first are information content studies (Beaver, 1968); the second, based on Ball & Brown (1968), are the valuation relevance studies; third, based on association testing between prices and accounting measures, are value relevance studies. According to Beaver, an event (announcement or disclosure) has information content if the price changes in excess of the amount due to the passage of time (i.e. expected return) when such an announcement is released. Beaver compares the value of U^2 (the error term) in the announcement period to the value of this function in the non-announcement period, and accordingly concludes that stock return variance is greater in the earnings announcement week.

Regarding value-added relevance studies, and consistent with market efficiency hypothesis, Ball & Brown (1968) assumed that capital markets are both efficient and unbiased in that, if information is useful in forming the capital asset price, the latter will then immediately be adjusted by the market in light of the released information, without leaving any possibility for abnormal gain. Since in the real world the efficient market hypothesis does not operate and many other (weaker) forms, such as semi-strong or weak forms, might do, the findings of this research are undermined.

The focus of the valuation relevance approach (Ball & Brown, 1968) is on one or more specific accounting summary measures. In the Ball & Brown research, it was the earnings, and how these summary measures related to price changes. The summary measures are said to be valuation-relevant if the sign of this measure is positively related to changes in stock price. Following these, researchers used the magnitude of the slope coefficient of a linear regression of returns on net income as a metric of the extent to which earnings are less or more relevant in explaining returns (Collins & Kothari 1989).

The value-relevance approach discusses the association between market value and accounting summary measures, such as earnings and book value. Formally, this approach requires that not only should the summary measure be identified by researchers, but so should the valuation method that links this measure to prices. Under this assumption, a summary measure (performance measure) is said to be value relevant if it connects to market values significantly enough (Holthausen & Watts 2000).

Thus, this study is established to answer several questions: Does profit warning lead to abnormal stock price informativeness throughout the announcement periods amongst Jordanian firms? Is there any association between profit warning types and stock price informativeness in Jordanian firms? Does the firm size relate to the profit warning effect on stock prices across Jordanian firms? To achieve the main aim, this work investigated the association between profit warnings and stock price informativeness, and accordingly tested whether any of the measures examined is able to explain variation in stock price informativeness.

3. Study Designed

3.1. Study Sample

The initial sample consists of 810 firm-years of Jordanian firms listed on the Amman Stock Exchange (ASE), with available data on DataStream databases for the period between 2005 and 2016. Following prior research banking, insurance, and other financial sector firms were excluded from the sample; this was owing to the fact that these sectors have special regulations and financial accounting standards, and the inclusion of these sectors in the sample could potentially distort the research results. Qualitative and quantitative techniques were used to explore the relationship between profit warnings and stock price informativeness in previous studies. This study used a quantitative technique in order to measure profit warnings (Skinner, 1994) since the data available in the Amman stock market meets quantitative requirements. As for qualitative methods, there is no information available, i.e. announcement of potential profit warnings, in the Amman stock market.

3.2. Stock Price Synchronicity

Our measure of stock price informativeness is based on stock price synchronicity. In particular, this study considers the amount of firm-specific stock return variation as an indicator of the amount of firm-specific information that is incorporated into the stock price, thus as an indicator of the informativeness of the stock price. A higher firm-specific stock return variation reflects a lower correlation between stock returns and the market, as well as industry returns, thereby suggesting that stock prices are more likely to reflect firm-specific information (French & Roll, 1986; Roll, 1988); hence, stock prices are less synchronous with market return and industry return.

Each calendar year, the research estimate firm-specific measure of stock return synchronicity through the use of the methodology outlined in the following prior studies (Piotroski & Roulstone, 2004; Gul, Kim *et al.* 2010; Kim & Shi 2012; An & Zhang 2013; Boubaker, Mansali *et al.* 2014). Specifically, for each firm's yearly observation, the model regresses the firm *i*'s weekly returns on the current week's and prior week's value weighted average market return and the current week's and prior week value weighted average two digit SIC code industry return:

$$RET_{i,w} = \alpha + \beta_1 MKRET_{w1} + \beta_2 MKRET_{w-1} + \beta_3 INDRET_{i,w1} + \beta_4 INDRET_{i,w-1} + \epsilon_{i,w}$$

where:

$RET_{i,w}$ is the weekly return for firm i in week w , $MKRET_w$ is the value-weighted market return for week w , $MKRET_{w-1}$ is the value-weighted market returns for week $w-1$, $INDRET_{i,w}$ is the industry value-weighted return excluding firm i 's weekly return for week w , and $INDRET_{i,w-1}$ is the industry value-weighted return excluding firm i 's weekly return for week $w-1$.

The industry return ($INDRET_{i,w}$) for a specific week for the industry of firm i is created using all the firms with the same two digit SIC code, with firm i 's weekly return omitted. Here ($INDRET_{i,w}$) is the value weighted average of these firms' week w return. To correct for any potential autocorrelation problem, a similar method as that implemented by Piotroski & Roulstone (2004), Kim & Shi (2012a) and Ben-Nasr & Alshwer (2016) was used with the inclusion of the lagged value of weekly market return and weekly industry returns in the regression model. Following Piotroski & Roulstone (2004) and An & Zhang (2013), the model uses weekly returns as opposed to daily returns when calculating stock price synchronicity. An & Zhang (2013) justify the use of weekly return as opposed to daily returns, as an attempt to avoid the problems linked to thinly traded stocks.¹ In addition, the model excludes the firm i 's weekly return when calculating the industry return so as to prevent spurious correlation in industry sectors dominated by few firms (An & Zhang, 2013). Finally, so as to avoid firms that went public, were delisted or which otherwise experienced trading halts, the model follows Piotroski & Roulstone (2004) and excludes those firms whose shares trade for less than 45 weeks over a fiscal year during the sample period.

Since the R-squared value obtained from the above regression model cannot be used as a dependent variable owing to it being bounded between unity and zero and it being highly skewed, this research follows the work of Boubaker, Mansali *et al.* (2014), Kim & Shi (2012) and Piotroski & Roulstone (2004), and further applies a logistic transformation that allows the transformed variable to range from negative infinity to positive infinity. Accordingly, stock price synchronicity can be calculated for each firm in each sample year as follows:

$$SYNCH_{i,t} = \log \left(\frac{R_{i,t}^2}{1 - R_{i,t}^2} \right)$$

where:

$R_{i,t}^2$ is the coefficient of determination from the estimation of Eq (1) for firm i in year t . The log transformation of $R_{i,t}^2$ creates an unbounded continuous variable out of a variable originally bounded by zero and one, yielding a dependent variable with a more normal distribution (Piotroski & Roulstone, 2004).

$SYNCH$ is measured for each firm during each year in the sample. By construction, the high value of $SYNCH$ indicates that individual firms' stock returns tend to co-move more closely with the market and/or the industry return; thus, firm-specific return variation is small. This means that a higher value of $SYNCH$ causes firm stock price movement to be largely explained by the market and industry return, which means that the stock price reflects less firm-specific information relative to market and/or industry common information; hence, stock price is considered to be less informative in regards firms' fundamental value. As a robustness test, the synchronicity is calculated by regressing the firm i 's weekly returns on the current week's value weighted average market return and the current week's value weighted average two digit SIC code industry return

$$RET_{i,w} = \alpha + \beta_1 MKRET_w + \beta_2 INDRET_{i,w} + \epsilon_{i,w}.$$

¹Thinly traded stocks are the stocks that exchanged in low volumes and often have a limited number of interested buyers and seller.

3.3. Analysis and Discussion

Descriptive Statistics and Univariate Analysis

This section discloses the descriptive statistics and univariate analysis findings for our study variables, which measure the association between profit warnings and stock price informativeness in Jordanian firms. Furthermore, the researchers present descriptive measures for the control variables. Table 1 reports the descriptive statistics for the variables used in the empirical model. The mean value of stock price synchronicity is (-1.47)—notably much higher than for the US, the UK and Australia—suggesting that the US, the UK and Canadian markets incorporate more firm specific information into stock price than Jordanian markets. This result is in line with the results of Morck, Yeung *et al.* (2000), which state that stock price in developed countries, with better accounting information, exhibit lower stock price synchronicity than those in less developed countries.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics and Univariate Test

Model Sample					
Variables	Median	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation
SYNC	-1.68	-4.97	1.28	-1.47	1.09
PWPR	0.00	-368.29	74.19	-0.87	17.14
MTB	0.84	-14.23	500.13	1.71	17.67
ROA	0.24	-195.30	84.07	0.16	12.35
ROE	0.00	-34544.15	8002.76	-32.28	1247.74
DR	26.15	0.00	227.53	29.63	27.41
ER	60.44	-127.53	99.60	51.69	34.05
IND	132.00	0.00	242.00	119.61	53.15

SYNC is Stock Price Synchronicity, PWPR is Profit Warnings Percentage, MTB is Market to Book Value, ROA is Return on Assets, ROE is Return on Equity, DR is Debt Ratio, ER is Equity Ratio, and IND is Industrial Type.

Correlation Matrix

Table 2 presents the Pearson correlations between the variables included in our regressions. Several key relations are present: first, there is negative correlation between stock price synchronicity and profit warnings, where such a negative correlation adoption provides an initial indication that profit warnings encourage investors to collect and process firm-specific information, leading to more informative stock price. In this regard, MTB, ROA, DR, ER, display negative correlation with stock price synchronicity, suggesting that firms with higher growth opportunities, higher profitability and higher leverage tend to have more informative stock price. Chun, Kim *et al.* (2008) argue that high-growth opportunity may be related to high firm-specific return variation owing to the fact that firms with high-growth opportunities have high intrinsic risk factors. Beuselinck, Joos *et al.* (2010) expect a negative relationship between stock price synchronicity and a firm's financial leverage ratio, suggesting that firms with high financial leverage have higher intrinsic risk factors, which may enforce investors to collect firm-specific information. ROE shows positive correlation with synchronicity. We generally report low correlation coefficients between stock price synchronicity and our control variables, mitigating concerns that multicollinearity could affect our regression results.

Table 2: Pearson Correlation for Firms in the Model Sample

	SYNC	PWPR	MTB	ROA	ROE	DR	ER	IND
SYNC	1.000							
PWPR	-0.017	1.000						
MTB	-0.019	-0.001	1.000					
ROA	-0.034	-0.001	-0.133	1.000				
ROE	0.018	-0.002	-	0.134	1.000			
DR	-0.133*	-0.023	0.101**	-0.230**	-0.065	1.000		
ER	-0.397*	-0.007	-0.028	0.193	0.038	-0.217*	1.000	
IND	-0.259*	-0.028	0.017	0.014	0.000	0.080	0.311*	1.000

SYNC is Stock Price Synchronicity, PWPR is Profit Warnings Percentage, MTB is Market to Book Value, ROA is Return on Assets, ROE is Return on Equity, DR is Debt Ratio, ER is Equity Ratio, and IND is Industrial Type.

Notes: indicate significant at *** 0.001, ** 0.05, * 0.10

Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), Tolerance (1/VIF) Tests and Heteroskedasticity Test

In this section, we present and discuss the results of variances inflation factor (VIF) and tolerance results. Prior literature documented that ‘if VIF test is less than 10 and tolerance test is more than 0.2 that means there is no multi-collinearity’ (e.g., Hair, Black, Babin & Anderson, 2010; Rahman & Ali, 2006; Graham, 2003). Table 3 shows that market-to-book value (MTB) and return on equity (ROE) variables have values of VIF greater than 10, and tolerance values less than 0.2, meaning that collinearity is an issue in this research.

Table 3: VIF and Tolerance Results for Model Sample

Variable	VIF	Tolerance
MTB	16.670	0.060
ROE	16.600	0.060
ER	1.210	0.824
DR	1.150	0.871
IND	1.140	0.879
ROA	1.100	0.912
PWPR	1.000	0.999
Mean VIF	5.5	

Heteroscedasticity means that the variances of random errors in ordinary least square regression (OLS) are inconsistent (Kaufman 2013). Consequently, the heteroscedasticity problem likelihood occurs when the magnitude of the residuals seems to be correlated to independent variable value. Non-parametric tests, such as white robust regression, fixed effect regression and generalised least square regression (GLS), are all recognised as alternative ways to solve the heteroscedasticity problem (Kaufman 2013; Hair *et al.* 2010).

In this section, the Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test was applied in order to determine whether the dataset of this research has been impacted by the heteroscedasticity problem. Table 4 shows that the model sample has been affected from heteroscedasticity since the chi2 value is (17.06) and they are significant at the (0.008) level, meaning that we have to reject the null hypothesis that states ‘all variances of random errors in OLS regression for model sample is constant’ and accepted the alternative hypothesis that stated ‘there is inconstant in variances of random errors in all model’.

Table 4: Heteroskedasticity Results

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for	
Ho: Constant variance	
Variables: fitted values of V	
Chi²(1)	17.06
Prob > chi²	0.008

Based on the aforementioned results in tables 3 and 4, which have presented a real problem in terms of existing multi-collinearity and heteroscedasticity problems, this research used white robust regression rather than OLS regression (see Appendix 1 for OLS regression results).

White Robust Regression

Firms’ financial leverage (DR) shows a significant negative effect on stock price synchronicity with p-value < 0.001. Hutton, Marcus *et al.* (2009) suggest that firms’ financial leverage is expected to have an effect on stock price synchronicity through its impacts on the sensitivity of firms’ return to macroeconomic conditions and because it influences the division of risk-bearing between equity shareholders and debtors. Moreover, Beuselinck & Joos *et al.* (2010) expect a positive relation between firm-specific return variation and firms’ financial leverage ratio, suggesting that firms with high financial leverage have high intrinsic risk factors that could potentially enforce investors to collect firm-specific information. Accordingly, these results support the previous argument. The negative effect of (DR) on stock price synchronicity (SYNCH1) is in line with the findings of Kim & Yi (2015), Yu, Li *et al.* (2013), Kim & Shi (2012) and Gul & Srinidhi *et al.* (2011), who document a negative effect of firms’ financial leverage on firm stock price synchronicity. These results support the view that data for firms with high financial leverage is more valuable for the reason that investors try to collect, process and trade on this information, leading to higher firm-specific return variation for high leveraged firms.

Market to book ratio (MTB), which is used to measure firms’ growth opportunities, records positive effect on stock price synchronicity. Hutton, Marcus *et al.* (2009) argue that the market-to-book ratio places firms along a growth-versus-value spectrum and thus could be systematically related to firm-specific return variation. Consistent with the findings of An & Zhang (2013) and Yu, Li *et al.* (2013), the estimated coefficient of (MTB) is significantly positive. This result suggests that firms with high growth opportunities tend to have a more synchronous stock price.

Firms’ performance and profitability, as measured by the ratio of net income to total equity (ROE). is expected to have an effect on stock price synchronicity. Ben-Nasr & Cosset (2014) and

Gul, Srinidhi *et al.* (2011) expect a positive relationship between return on assets and stock price synchronicity, indicating that more profitable firms tend to have less informative stock price.

PWPR shows a significant negative effect on stock price synchronicity. This means that firms with higher profit warnings incorporate more firm-specific information into stock price. This result is in line with our prediction that higher profit warning will encourage firm investors to collect and process more firm-specific information than common market information. Previous research supports this assumption (Ferreira & Laux, 2007) mention that accounting information is a central component of information flow to the market. Biddle, Seow *et al.* (1995), Francis, Schipper *et al.* (2003) and Liu, Nissim *et al.* (2002) also document that investors depend on earnings numbers in their decisions more so than any other measure of performance. In addition, Francis, LaFond *et al.* (2004) assert that earnings numbers are an importance source of firm-specific information. Furthermore, Cox, Dayanandan *et al.* (2017) find that profit warnings are associated with abnormal return during the course of the announcement day, meaning that the investor uses this firm-specific information in their investment decisions.

Table 5: White Robust Regression for Model Sample

	ROA	
	Coef.	t
PWPR	-0.002	-2.08**
MTB	0.012	3.85***
ROA	-0.001	-0.24
ROE	0.000	4.32***
DR	-0.009	-6.70***
ER	-0.013	-12.09***
IND	-0.002	-3.68****
T-statistics	64.15***	
R²	22.35%	

White Robust Regression under Corporate Governance Characteristics as Moderate Variable

In this section, the researchers went further to test the impact of corporate governance characteristics on the relationship between stock price informativeness and profit warnings. Prior literature document that strong corporate governance characteristics is positively related to announcing good earnings news in the near future. In this regard, Karamanou & Vafeas (2015) investigate the ways that could potentially lead a Board of Directors and audit committee characteristics to affect the level of voluntary financial disclosure practices, where earnings forecasts are used as a proxy. Their empirical results documented that firms with a stronger Board and audit committee characteristics are more likely related to good updates, which, in turn, leads to increased opportunities for attracting more investors.

According to the theoretical notion of agency costs developed by Jensen & Meckling (1976), Jensen (2005) studied the way in which firm government quality and its decisions could relate to the issue of profit warning, particularly when overestimated. In this regard, and based on a sample of Canadian firms reviewed during the period 2000–2004, Jensen (2005) presents results that partially support this hypothesis. For example, factors pertaining to Board of Directors, such as Board size, Board insiders and outsiders, and Board independence, are more likely to affect the decision to issue a profit warning when the firm is overestimated.

Alternatively, other governance mechanisms, such as ownership structure, are negatively related to the profit-warning pronouncement.

Accordingly, we extracted new independent variables by multiplying an independent variable (PWPR) with some Board of Directors characteristics (Board size, Board outsiders and Board insiders), and audit committee characteristics (audit committee size, audit committee meeting and audit committee expertise). Six new variables have been established, namely profit warnings and board size (PWBSIZE), profit warnings and board outsider (PWOUTS), profit warnings and board insider (PWBINS), profit warnings and audit committee size (PWACSIZE), profit warnings and audit committee meeting (PWACMEET), and profit warnings and audit committee expertise (PWACEXP). These variables calculated as through equations (1 to 6):

$$PWBSIZE = PWPR * Board Size \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$PWBINS = PWPR * Board Insider \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

$$PWOUTS = PWPR * Board Outsider \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

$$PWACSIZE = PWPR * Audit Committee Size \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

$$PWACMEET = PWPR * Audit Committee Meeting \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

$$PWACEXP = PWPR * Audit Committee Expertise \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

However, OLS regression still has VIF and Heteroskedasticity problems, even following the addition of extracting new independent variables. Therefore, white's robust regression was used in this section to overcome these two problems. Our results show improvement in the relationship between main profit warnings and stock price informativeness, since Table 5 shows (-2.08) at the 1% level and Table 6 after adding corporate governance characteristics shows (-2.15). These results are consistent with prior studies (Karamanou & Vafeas, 2015; Ferreira & Laux, 2007).

In our case, OLS estimates are unbiased and consistent, but nonetheless inefficient. In addition, OLS has a habit of underestimating the parameter standard errors, which, in turn, affect the association between profit warnings through the use of corporate governance characteristics as moderate variables. Consequently, the white robust regression is proposed to generate a most favourable unbiased estimator of β for satiations with Heteroskedasticity variance and to ensure that the association between variables is efficient (Carroll, 2017). Accordingly, this study has adopted a non-parametric test (whites robust regression) as a multivariate test technique to explore the influence of corporate governance characteristics on the relationship between stock price informativeness and profit warnings in Jordanian firms as opposed to parametric test (OLS regression), where most OLS regression assumptions do not meet the study dataset (see Appendix 2).

Our findings, as detailed in Table 6, are partially consistent with Jensen (2015), where we found that Board insiders, Board outsiders, audit committee size and audit committee expertise are all positively influential in the relationship between profit warnings and stock price informativeness in Jordanian firms. On the other hand, Board size and audit committee have a negative impact on the relationship between profit warnings and stock price infromativeness. These results are not consistent with prior literature, such as those by Cox *et al.* (2017), Jensen (2015) and Francis *et al.* (2004). These results could refer to several reasons: corporate governance code differences, cultural factors, political and economic circumstances. Finally, our empirical evidence is approximately consistent with the notion that effective corporate governance impacts the relationship between stock price and profit warnings.

Table 6: White Robust Regression for Model Sample

	ROA	
	Coef.	t
PWPR	-0.002	-2.15**
PWBSIZE	-0.855	-4.06***
PWBINS	0.819	3.92***
PWOUTS	0.774	3.77***
PWACSIZE	0.158	2.43**
PWACMEET	-0.156	-3.06***
PWACEXP	0.212	1.85*
MTB	0.010	3.18***
ROA	-0.001	-0.29
ROE	0.000	3.77***
DR	-0.008	-5.77***
ER	-0.012	-11.06***
IND	-0.003	-4.32***
T-statistics	42.47***	
R²	26.49%	

4. Conclusion

In this study, we examined the effect of profits warnings announcement on the amount of firm-specific information incorporated into stock price, as inversely measured by stock informativeness. Profit warnings referred to the announcements made by publicly listed companies, prior to the presentation of their formal financial statements, to warn users of their financial data, to communicate that their earnings would be different to previously expected levels. Profit warnings can be either positive or negative. We expect a positive effect of profit warnings on stock price informativeness. As prior research suggests, a possible link between profit warnings and the informativeness of stock price can be seen, where Cox, Dayanandan *et al.* (2017) find that firms' profit warnings are associated with abnormal return during announcement days, suggesting that investors use this firm-specific information in their investment decisions. Consistent with our prediction, the results show a significant positive effect of profit warnings on the amount of firm-specific information incorporated into stock price.

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Appendices

Appendix (1) OLS Regression Results for the Model Sample

	Coef.	t	P>t
PWPR	0.00	-0.89	
MTB	0.01	1.59	
ROA	0.00	-0.20	
ROE	0.00	1.70	*
DR	-0.01	-6.63	***
ER	-0.01	-11.96	***
IND	0.00	-3.54	***
Adj R²	22.35%		
Adj R² Adj	21.67%		
T statistics	32.97***		
Prob. t	0.000		

SYNC is Stock Price Synchronicity, PWPR is Profit Warnings Percentage, MTB is Market to Book Value, ROA is Return on Assets, ROE is Return on Equity, DR is Debt Ratio, ER is Equity Ratio, and IND is Industrial Type.

Notes: indicate significant at *** 0.001, ** 0.05, * 0.10

Appendix (2) OLS Regression Results for the Model Sample with Corporate Governance

	ROA	
	Coef.	t
PWPR	-0.002	-0.99
PWBSIZE	-0.855	-4.13***
PWBINS	0.819	4.00***
PWOUTS	0.774	3.84***
PWACSIZE	0.158	2.39**
PWACMEET	-0.156	-3.11***
PWACEXP	0.212	1.82*
MTB	0.010	1.24
ROA	-0.001	-0.25
ROE	0.000	1.38
DR	-0.008	-5.90***
ER	-0.012	-11.30***
IND	-0.003	-4.140***
T-statistics	22.07***	
R²	26.49%	
Adj. R²	25.29	